

TRANSITIONING TO CLINICAL PRACTICE WITHOUT INDUCTION PROGRAMS: A JOURNAL OF NEWLY-REGISTERED NURSES

Harry Emmanuel C. Ayta, Nel Ivan G. Alta, Nathaniel L. Dilao, Ian C. Abordo, PhD,
Donna Belle P. Sumugat, RN, MAN, and Raymond M. Salvador, RN, MN

Nursing Department, Adventist Medical Center College, Iligan City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13734341>

ABSTRACT

Transitioning to clinical practice after obtaining a license presents issues and challenges, particularly for nurses who have not received any training or induction. This study aimed to understand the lived experiences of newly licensed nurses who did not undergo any formal training or induction program during their transition to professional practice. A descriptive phenomenological approach was employed, utilizing online semi-structured interviews to gather data from registered nurses. A total of nine participants were selected using purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted through van Manen's (1997) lifeworld existentials, categorizing the data in lifeworld concepts such as lived space, lived time, lived human relations, lived body, and lived technology. New nurses experienced significant physical and emotional challenges from time, space, and relation aspects of the work environments. Despite these challenges, many nurses developed resilience and confidence through coping, workplace support and self-discovery. Ten themes emerged. The study contributes to the understanding of the challenges faced by new nurses and provides insights for improving the transition process. The findings underscore the need for supportive work environments, structured programs, and peer support to help new nurses in the transition to professional practice.

Keywords: *lived experiences, newly licensed nurses, transition, student to professional practice, physical and emotional challenges, phenomenology*

INTRODUCTION

The transition from student to registered nurse (RN) is a difficult phase recognized globally. During this phase, new graduate nurses are confronted with several challenges, such as work overload and unsupportive work environments that can affect their professional life and transition experiences (Dames, 2019). Newly graduated nurses face a multitude of emotions, uncertainties, and stressors during this transition to clinical practice (Duchscher, 2009). These challenges have been linked to negative emotional states, including stress, depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem among nurses (Labrague & McEnroe-Petite, 2018).

Stress in the hospital setting arises from various factors. These include inexperience, negative outcomes, administering incorrect treatments, and heavy workloads (Mazzella-Ebstein et al. 2021). Newly licensed nurses face heightened stress when handling clinically unstable patients, multitasking, caring for critically ill or dying patients, and dealing with demanding families (Duchscher and Windey 2018). Those with stress-related symptoms are less satisfied with their jobs and are more likely to consider leaving the profession (Laschinger et al., 2016; Kaihlanen et al., 2016).

If not mitigated, transition shock compromises patient safety outcomes. New nurses in the ER who experienced transition shock had heightened emotional exhaustion, leading to increased adverse patient events and a decline in nursing care quality (Zhang et al., 2023). Other new graduate nurses expressed that workplace deficiencies served as a major source of frustration during the transition, which is a significant predictor of safety behavior, pointing out that new nurses who experienced less transition shock were more competent in avoiding patient harm and improving patient safety (Labrague, 2023).

Previous studies found that nurses who had preceptorship experienced a lesser degree of transition shock. According to Irwin et al. (2018), positive preceptorship boosts confidence with professional skills and strengthens commitment to the nursing role. Compassion, support systems, and sharing coping experiences also contribute to preventing discouragement and enhancing performance confidence (Roze des Ordons et al., 2018). Supporting preceptor development for new graduate nurses, particularly with well-trained preceptors, positively impacts their confidence in delivering safe patient care (Clipper & Cherry, 2015).

Preceptorship, while addressing transition challenges, poses difficulties due to stress and lack of support (Lewis & McGowan, 2015; Quek & Shorey, 2018). Increased stress levels and reluctance among preceptors' stem from the demanding role and patient workload. Staff shortages make assigning one preceptor to one new graduate nurse challenging (Wierzbinski-Cross et al., 2015). Consequently, the suitability of preceptorship as the primary solution to transition shock remains uncertain.

Transition shock, evident in anxiety and feelings of incompetence during the process, may seem daunting but can be mitigated with adjustments to the nursing transition process. A supportive work team and positive environment aid graduate nurses in coping

and fostering personal and professional growth (Wakefield, 2018). While successful preceptorship helps novices adapt to clinical settings, it may not be the sole solution.

To address transition shock, new nurse graduates must focus on developing nursing competence through preceptorship. The knowledge-practice gap hinders critical problem-solving in clinical settings (Lee & Oh, 2020), especially when managing uncertain patient conditions (Kukkonen et al., 2019). Improving critical thinking during education is crucial (Chen et al., 2021). Educational programs should target critical thinking and research aptitude, both during education and post-registration. Maintaining a fixed one-on-one preceptor relationship is essential for safe skill performance (Irwin et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021). While the literature is clear that transition shock is a common problem, current transition programs concentrate on knowledge and skills, neglecting emotional, sociocultural, and developmental aspects (Rush et al., 2019). There is a need to refine existing methods for a more comprehensive approach.

Research Questions

The main research questions were:

1. What are the key experiences and feelings of newly licensed nurses during their transition to the professional practice?
2. What were the challenges that the newly licensed nurses encountered during the transition?
3. How do newly licensed nurses cope with the experience of transition in the clinical environment?
4. What is the meaning of these experiences to their professional life?

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research was conducted using descriptive phenomenology. The study drew on the concepts of lived space, time, human relations, body, and technology from the framework of lifeworld existentials to explore the participants' experiences and meanings. (Heidegger, 1927; Merleau-Ponty, 1945; Husserl, 1913). By concentrating on exploration as an essential aim, we evoke flexibility that allows researchers to shift between lines of inquiry and move from one activity to another to uncover the structure of the experience (Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022).

Population and Sample

Dukes (1984) emphasized that a sample size of one is theoretically sufficient, as the goal is to uncover the necessary invariants of an experience, which can be discovered in any individual case. However, he noted that it is wise to expand the sample size to include multiple subjects to ensure that the findings are not distorted by the researcher's biases or the contingent facts of a particular case. The study required samples who are licensed nurses and have experienced the transition from student to professional practice without going through an induction program. Thus, qualitative researchers would focus on the

selection of individuals and settings either purposeful sampling or criterion-based sampling (Patton, 2002).

Instrumentation

This study employed a data collection approach using online semi-structured interviews to explore the experiences of newly licensed nurses during their transition to professional practice. Semi-structured interviews, according to Smith et al. (2009), facilitate rapport, allow flexibility, and yield richer data by enabling the conversation to cover new areas. Conducted with one respondent at a time, these interviews use open-ended questions to delve into key experiences and challenges faced by new nurses, accompanied by follow-up questions to gain deeper insights (Adams, 2015). This method is ideal for capturing participants' opinions, feelings, attitudes, and beliefs about their job and the overall transition from student to professional nurse.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers obtained a signed permission letter from the Dean of Nursing at Adventist Medical Center College and the research advisor. Informed consent was secured from all participants, who were assured of their voluntary participation and the option to withdraw at any time. Also guaranteeing confidentiality and emphasizing the absence of harm. Additionally, participants' dignity and rights were respected, and all procedures and the purpose of the study was thoroughly explained.

Data Gathering Procedure

An online semi-structured interview was conducted individually on the participants to discuss their lived experiences as newly registered nurses. The researchers captured an audio recording of every participant interview about their experiences during their transition to professional practice. To initiate the sharing of their experiences, the initial question for the participants was simply presented as like, "What were the key experiences that you had as a newly licensed nurse?" This question is open-ended and intended for the participant for the researchers to pull out particular information.

Data Analysis

The analysis was conducted using the descriptive phenomenology categorizing the data in lifeworld concepts such as lived space, lived time, lived human relations, lived body, and lived technology. Van Manen (1997) suggests that many experiences can be understood as corresponding to these lifeworld existentials, they present helpful guides through which to explore a phenomenon under investigation. This helps to understand the context and interpret the participants opinion and/or life-story that expresses the lived experiences of transitioning and the challenges encountered as a new licensed nurse.

RESULTS

The data from nine participants were used in this study — registered nurses working in various roles across different nursing departments. Among the participants, seven were female and two were male, whose ages ranged from 23 to 37. All participants graduated with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree. Seven participants were employed in the hospital setting, one in the community, and one in the home settings. None of the participants were formally trained prior to working as professional nurses (see Table 1).

Table 1
Participants' Demographic Profile

<i>Participant Code</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Months Working as A Nurse</i>	<i>Work Setting</i>
Vib	37	Graduate of BSN	Female	120 months	Personal/Home Nurse
Jim	33	Graduate of BSN	Male	96 months	Community Nurse
Chloe	23	Graduate of BSN	Female	48 months	Staff Nurse
Vans	24	Graduate of BSN	Female	79 months	OR Nurse
Klu	33	Graduate of BSN	Female	48 months	Staff Nurse
Cruz	23	Graduate of BSN	Female	3 months	OR Nurse
Blanz	24	Graduate of BSN	Female	11 months	OR Nurse
Cai	23	Graduate of BSN	Male	63 months	General Ward Nurse
Rhea	23	Graduate of BSN	Female	63 months	Pediatric Ward Nurse

The audio from the online interviews conducted with the participants were recorded and transcribed. After the data was analyzed, major themes that highlighted the lived experiences of the respondents emerged from the research study. The themes identified were:

Theme 1: Under-resourced and Disorganized Hospital Environment

New nurses experienced working in a hospital environment with a disorganized layout, lack of equipment, and space constraints. They described having to run between essential areas, such as equipment rooms and pharmacies due to the distance and the layout, which made it difficult to access the supplies and medicine quickly for patient care. Lack of equipment or malfunctioning resources impeded productivity and patient care for these new nurses. New nurses found themselves waiting to use shared computers to input patient data and document care activities. One of the nurses described:

“AMCV is not a big hospital. The nursing station is smaller compared to other hospitals. So, you just have to make do with the space you have. In our area, we aren't very exposed to the outside world. Sometimes, it's surprising to realize that it's almost time to leave because we haven't seen the outside. It's somewhat depressing because you can't see nature or the outdoors. Our hospital is small, and when we go downstairs, it's quite far because we use stairs... although we have an elevator, it is sometimes off or under maintenance. So, when we need medicine, we have to run to the pharmacy on the first floor and then return to the third floor. It's very tiring, and not everything is easily accessible. Honestly, we don't have many advanced tools, though we do use some technology. For example, we have computers where we input everything. In one station, we have only two computers for three nurses and one senior nurse, so we have to make the most of our time, sometimes taking turns because we don't each have our own computer. Patients' data and their medication information need to be input into the computer. Our system isn't very advanced, especially for doctors' orders, which are still written manually. Unlike other hospitals where doctors input orders directly into the computer, this is an area where we are a bit behind.” (Blanz, RN)

Theme 2: Time Management Challenges

New nurses faced issues in managing their time because of disturbed schedules, time constraints, shifting work environments, and performing a variety of jobs like charting, administering medications to patients, carrying out doctor's orders, and fulfilling various requests from watchers or patients. These unforeseen events affected their schedule, resulting in time management challenges as they adapted to changing priorities. The respondents also mentioned that things happened too fast and not having enough time to complete the tasks that needed to be done. The respondents articulated:

“First, the time when I was still a student nurse, it was tough to manage our time because we had so many tasks, there were clinicals, academics, but when I became a nurse, I expected to have more time for myself, which didn't happen now, it's still so hard, the changes I experienced. I have a boyfriend, but we broke up because he couldn't understand or manage our time together. Because, as a nurse, I can't just choose my schedule if I want to have all morning shifts or all evening shifts... I have no control over my schedule, my time, and we had a misunderstanding, that's one change I experienced when I became a nurse that's proving quite difficult.” (Vans, RN)

Theme 3: Self-Reliance from Lack of Guidance

During the transition, new nurses experienced intimidation from those with higher positions because of the significant power dynamic difference between them. Higher figures such as doctors and senior nurses have greater authority and expertise. The new nurses worried about making mistakes and needed guidance. So new nurses dealt with situations where they had to learn and practice independently, without relying on others, adapting quickly to new and challenging situations on their own. This self-reliance and ability to constantly handle challenges without guidance were important for the learning and development of new nurses. A respondent mentioned:

“When you work in a hospital, you don't have someone to rely on like you did as a student. It's also challenging to deal with strict doctors, as they can be demanding. Also, you know, when you're working with other people, not everyone is easy to get along with. Especially when I worked internationally, not in the Philippines, there were other people who were not very welcoming. There will always be people who discriminate, you can't really avoid it. They thought that since I worked in a hospital, I was qualified and knew everything. It was a challenge for me because, especially when asking for help from them, they would question if I knew anything at all. They would talk about you to others, trying to belittle you. It made me feel discriminated against; they wouldn't approach me because they thought I didn't know anything. So that's how it was...The significant impact on my learning and development as a nurse was that I had to learn and practice on my own, without relying on anyone. I had to improve my skills and apply procedures like bed baths, suctioning for tracheostomy, etc. without guidance, which was very challenging and dangerous for my license” (Vib, RN)

Theme 4: Communication and Interpersonal Skills

New nurses faced numerous challenges including dealing with distressed patients or their families, managing multiple tasks, and resolving conflicts among team members. New nurses used effective communication and interpersonal skills in navigating these situations calmly and professionally. New nurses learned these skills through their experiences, not by following a book but by adapting to the demands of their new roles. Resolving the worries of the patients' families were challenging for new nurses. New nurses experienced difficult conversations and prejudice from patients' families who preferred more experienced nurses. One of the nurses shared:

“As I mentioned, I wasn't communicative before. Now, as a nurse, I have to practice being an effective communicator because it's a crucial part of nursing. It's not just in the books; it's also about real-life experience. If you hesitate or fail to respond properly, it could negatively impact the patient's care” (Jim, RN)

Theme 5: Physical and Emotional Challenges

New nurses experienced a multitude of physical and emotional challenges during their adjustment. They had to adapt to extended work hours and shift rotations which lead to significant fatigue and hampered their circadian rhythms, causing changes in sleeping patterns. They also experienced doing heavy lifting, repetitive movements, and prolonged

periods of standing and walking, which resulted in physical exhaustion and attrition. New nurses experienced stress and anxiety in making decisions and feeling the weight of their patients' lives at their hands which was mentally draining. The respondents described having feelings of being shocked, nervousness, and overwhelm during their work. A respondent expressed:

“Mentally draining and physically exhausting especially if you're a fresh graduate, but then it's a part of the transition. In the long run, your body will adjust, especially to the shifting schedule. So, during the morning shift, the physical stress is intense, doctors make rounds, and there are numerous procedures in the morning. During the afternoon shift, there are continuous orders from the morning. During the night shift, it's somewhat relaxing as most patients are sleeping; you administer medication and then let the patient rest throughout the night.” (Klu, RN)

Theme 6: Stress Management and Coping

New nurses experienced using stress management strategies to maintain well-being and provide quality care during the transition phase. Taking breaks and getting fresh air allowed them to disconnect from the high-stress hospital environment. New nurses also engaged in hobbies and enjoyable activities outside of work provided them time to unwind and relax, reducing stress. Support from colleagues and the enjoyment of learning was a source of motivation to stay focused despite challenges. A change in mindset was also applied such as thinking about the salary. One of the nurses revealed:

“Well, if I'm feeling stressed while working, I usually step out for a few minutes to get some fresh air. I value my break time because that's when I can truly relax. After work, outside of work, life/work balance is crucial. Spending time with myself helps me deal with stress. For example, I enjoy taking walks. Just walking around, even if it's just window shopping, helps me relax. When I was in Dubai before moving to the UK, it was different. Here in the UK, they value work-life balance more. If you're feeling stressed, they give you a break. Holidays are essential here; they make sure we all get our time off. So, to deal with stress, we often go on holiday. The environment here is perfect for hiking, so that's what I do. Hiking allows me to get some fresh air and immerse myself in nature, which helps me unwind.” (Vib, RN)

Theme 7: Workplace Support

New nurses entering the clinical practice were challenged when adjusting to a new workplace. However, their experiences revealed that the support they received from colleagues helped them with their challenges. Some senior nurses maintained a professional distance, while others formed close relationships with their junior colleagues. This shift from seeing colleagues as mere coworkers to developing friendships provided a sense of familiarity and comfort in the workplace. It also helped the new nurses with their learning. One of the respondents said:

“As a student nurse, I was already aware of the burden that nurses carry when they become professionals, so it wasn't entirely new when I started working. However, the transition felt significant because the support from the community around you during your

start helps alleviate some of the anxiety about doing something you're unsure of.” (Rhea, RN)

Theme 8: Time Management Strategies and Prioritization

New nurses experienced increased workload and responsibility compared to their student days. They used effective time management to complete their tasks promptly. They also prioritized urgent or critical tasks to prevent errors and ensure timely patient care. New nurses emphasized meticulous planning, organization, and critical thinking to manage their workload. They used their clinical judgment to determine which patient issues require immediate attention. Through these strategies, they provided efficient care while managing the demands of the healthcare environment. One of the nurses expressed:

“Sometimes, my break time gets delayed because I don't go for breaks unless I finish what I need to do. For example, when I was working in the hospital before, I had to be mindful of the scheduled medications because I tend to forget them. So, I make sure to list down the specific times when I need to administer medications. For instance, if I need to give meds at 10 am, I list it down. Having these timings helps me manage my time better because I can prioritize important tasks while still having time for other things in between. Time management is crucial, so I focus on prioritizing essential tasks and may delay less critical ones. However, it's not always busy. There are times, especially during night duty, when it's less hectic compared to the day shift. During those times, I manage my time by listing the important tasks and ensuring I carry out doctors' orders and other necessary duties within the day.” (Vib, RN)

Theme 9: Role of Technology in Transitioning

New nurses used technology to bridge the gap between their academic education and the demands of real-world nursing practice. They encountered situations where they lacked knowledge and turned to resources like online tutorials or smartphone apps to learn independently, making it helpful in situations where information was on-demand. New nurses recognized the benefits of technology in enhancing their knowledge and skills, improving their abilities in providing quality patient care. They used technology to deliver better patient care by providing access to necessary information, facilitating communication with patients, and overcoming language barriers. A respondent claimed:

“At the beginning, when you're still figuring out how to do a procedure or what medications to use, especially for cases you encountered for the first time, because usually the pharmacology in college are only the common meds, but sometimes you encounter new things, so you have to search for them. At least when you enter the patient's room, you are able to say something like ‘This medication is for this’ so they won't be afraid to take it or whatever... Usually, I just rely on Google searches, sometimes YouTube, for procedures. I guess Google and YouTube only.” (Cai, RN)

Theme 10: Self-discovery and Shaping Identities

In their transition to professional practice, new nurses underwent a considerable transition from the academic setting to the reality of professional practice marked by challenges, growth, and self-discovery. From their experiences in the hospital, new nurses realized that real-world nursing needs more than just theoretical knowledge. The respondents emphasized the importance of support from colleagues, trusting their own instincts, and learning from experiences. As new nurses experience the transition, they feel a sense of fulfillment, enjoyment, and a growing love for the nursing profession. The continuous adjustment that new nurses experienced shaped their professional identities. One of the nurses stated:

“To be honest, the transition from being a student to being a nurse is quite significant. The theoretical knowledge we learned in school doesn't get applied as much in nursing practice. The practices in the clinical practice and the workplace are very different. In truth, there are many shortcuts that are not taught but are done to expedite work. It's significant that entering this profession wasn't easy, but with what I've learned now as a nurse, I enjoy it more, and I've grown to love my profession even more. But even though it's important to me, I still have a fear that... others might not see me as a proper or good nurse because perspectives vary, especially among us nurses or among you future nurses... not everyone has a positive view of nurses, so... you just have to accept everything and show respect to everyone, especially to patients, relatives, colleagues, and doctors.” (Vans, RN)

DISCUSSION

The findings revealed the key experiences of licensed nurses during their transition to professional practice and the essence of these experiences. This experience involves significant physical and emotional challenges. Physically, new nurses often struggle with the demands of time management and the chaotic nature of the hospital environment, which forced them to adapt to extended work hours, shift rotations, and physically demanding tasks. The lack of immediate guidance and the need for self-reliance in critical situations added to their stress. Additionally, working in disorganized hospital layouts, with old equipment and distant facilities, increased physical strain and hindered their capacity to perform tasks successfully. Emotionally, newly licensed nurses experienced negative workplace dynamics, often feeling targeted and unsupported by senior colleagues. In addition to a lack of information owing to being inexperienced, they suffered feelings of being overwhelmed, inadequacy, self-doubt, shock, worry, nervousness, or anxiety. To cope, new nurses relied on support from colleagues, participated in non-work-related activities, engaged in learning, and showed resilience by adjusting to their new surroundings.

The essence of these experiences profoundly shaped the professional lives of the participants. Overcoming initial challenges and hardships, and self-discovery contributed to their identities as competent professionals, enhancing their confidence and capability in patient care. Despite the hardships, the transition period gave them a sense of feeling fulfilled in their work and reinforced their commitment to nursing

New nurses experienced joy and a deepening love for their profession from their impactful roles in patient care. The growth and resilience developed during their transition had a positive influence on their characters, nurturing both their personal development and the quality of care they provide.

The findings of this study are consistent with prior studies on the problems experienced by newly licensed nurses. The present study's findings on the physical and emotional problems experienced by novice nurses when they transition to professional practice are consistent with previous research. Kramer (1974) first described the phenomenon of "reality shock" among newly licensed nurses, highlighting the disparity between educational preparation and the actual demands of clinical practice. This foundational theory is echoed in the current study's identification of significant physical demands and emotional stress experienced by new nurses. Additionally, Duchscher and Windey (2018) further elaborated on transition shock as encompassing physical, intellectual, emotional, developmental, and sociocultural changes, which is consistent with the multifaceted challenges highlighted in the current study.

Earlier studies have consistently documented high levels of stress among new graduate nurses due to transition shock. For example, Woo and Newman (2019) reported that while many new nurses' express satisfaction with their roles, a significant majority find the transition period extremely stressful. The findings of Woo and Newman (2019) parallels the emotional challenges of negative workplace dynamics, and feelings of inadequacy reported in the current study. Furthermore, coping mechanisms such as seeking peer support and continuous learning identified in the present research are supported by earlier studies like those of Alnuqaidan et al. (2021) and Tarhan et al. (2023) who explored the importance of social support and coping strategies in mitigating stress among new nurses.

The current study's findings on the development of professional identity and confidence through overcoming initial challenges resonate with Ortiz's (2016) research. Ortiz (2016) identified themes such as gaining experience, receiving positive feedback, and building relationships as crucial to developing professional confidence. This mirrors the current study's conclusion that the transition period, despite its difficulties, enhanced new nurses' confidence and commitment to their profession. The sense of professional fulfillment and the deepening love for the nursing profession reported in the current study align with the positive outcomes documented by Kaihlanen et al. (2016) and Cao et al. (2021) who emphasized the role of resilience and empathy in enhancing professional quality of life.

The importance of organizational support in easing the transition for new nurses is well-documented in the literature. Studies such as those by Su et al. (2020) and Su et al. (2023) highlight the significant role of clinical teaching behaviors and supportive work environments in reducing transition shock and improving career identity. The current study's findings on lack of support increasing the physical and emotional strain on new nurses is consistent with these earlier findings. Additionally, the effectiveness of structured support programs, like those mentioned by Rogers et al. (2023) and Zhang et

al. (2019), in improving work readiness and reducing turnover, further validates the current study's emphasis on the need for robust support systems for neophyte nurses. However, previous studies have not sufficiently addressed issues lack of resources and disorganized hospital layouts, for instance, inappropriate arrangement of the facilities was found to physically strain new nurses and taking turns using technology made their work less efficient. While previous literature discussed general support mechanisms and organizational factors affecting new nurses, it did not delve into the specific impact of the physical and spatial conditions of the workplace on the transition experiences of new nurses.

New nurses were also found to develop and utilize effective time management and prioritization strategies to cope with increased workloads and responsibilities. These strategies involve meticulous planning and critical thinking to handle tasks and patient care efficiently. This was not specifically covered by earlier studies which focused more broadly on the general challenges of transition shock, coping mechanisms, and organizational support.

Additionally, the study presented the role of clinical judgment in assessing patient concerns and prioritizing care. New nurses described the experience of urgent decision-making, using their clinical judgment to address immediate patient needs effectively. This practical aspect of transitioning to professional practice was not particularly talked about by previous literature, which centered on psychological and organizational factors.

The findings suggest the necessity for comprehensive support systems and organizational changes. Hospitals should create programs that address both emotional and practical challenges to facilitate the transition of newly licensed nurses. Literature consistently highlights the importance of supportive work environments and structured programs in mitigating transition shock (Su, 2020; Su, 2023).

The study also supports Duchscher and Windey's (2018) notion of multifaceted challenges, emphasizing the physical strain intensified by outdated facilities and the emotional stress from inadequate support. These imply need for improvements in the physical and workplace environment of hospitals to better support new nurses, complementing existing psychological and support-focused strategies.

As supported by Alnuqaidan et al. (2021) and Tarhan et al. (2023), fostering peer support and opportunities for continuous learning can help new nurses cope with the demands of the profession. Furthermore, enhancing professional identity and resilience, as discussed by Ortiz (2016) and Cao et al. (2021), can be achieved through targeted interventions such as mentorship programs and feedback mechanisms. Thus, healthcare institutions must invest in both infrastructure and policy changes to create a supportive and efficient environment for new nurses, ultimately improving job satisfaction and patient care outcomes.

Conclusions

In essence, the study found that new nurses experienced a range of challenges during their transition. Participants indicated that the hospital environment was physically and emotionally demanding, and they did not always get the support they need or have access to organized facilities leading to physical strain and causing stress and overwhelm. Despite these challenges, the study revealed that new nurses become more resilient and confident through work support, continuous learning, overcoming initial difficulties, and using coping mechanisms. It implies the need for better support systems and changes within structural organizations to help new nurses transition smoothly, improving work readiness and better patient care outcomes.

Recommendations

This study has several limitations. The participants were all graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing programs, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to nurses with different educational backgrounds. Majority of the participants were female, which might not capture the full spectrum of experiences across different gender distributions. Furthermore, the data were collected through online interviews, which may have limited the ability to observe non-verbal cues and might influence how participants articulate their experiences.

The researchers of this study recommend that future research should use a face-to-face interview approach to gather data to facilitate building of trust, leading to more in-depth responses. Also, including registered nurses from different degree levels may contribute to the diversity of the sample and the generalizability of the data. Longitudinal studies could provide more insights into how new nurses' experiences evolve over time. Additionally, exploring the impact of specific interventions, such as mentorship programs or changes in hospital policies, could further inform best practices for supporting new nurses.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In relations to the conditions of the study, several ethical considerations were carefully addressed. Before data collection began, informed consent was obtained from all of the participants, who were assured that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time. Permission was secured for audio recording the interviews, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the process, with an emphasis on ensuring that no harm would come to the participants. Furthermore, the dignity and rights of participants were respected, and all procedures, as well as the purpose of the study, were thoroughly explained. There were no conflicts of interest, and the study was conducted with a strong commitment to avoiding plagiarism. To address potential biases, the researchers employed the practice of bracketing, which allowed them to focus on the participants' perspectives rather than imposing their own interpretations. By recognizing and suspending their biases, the researchers helped prevent the misrepresentation of

participants' meanings and experiences, thereby ensuring the credibility of the research findings and demonstrating their dedication to upholding ethical principles.

Acknowledgments

We would like to take this opportunity to express our heartfelt gratitude to those who have supported us throughout our research journey, titled "Transitioning to Clinical Practice Without Induction Programs: A Journal of Newly-Registered Nurses."

First and foremost, we extend our deepest appreciation to our research director and advisor, Dr. Ian C. Abordo, PhD. Your encouragement, insightful evaluations, and most importantly your patience in guiding us have been instrumental in shaping our research. Your expertise has inspired us to explore our topic with depth and rigor.

We would also like to thank our esteemed panelists, Ms. Donna Belle P. Sumugat, RN, MAN, and Mr. Raymond M. Salvador, RN, MN. Your constructive critiques and thoughtful questions during our thesis defense challenged us to refine our work and think critically about our findings. We are grateful for your support and insights.

Lastly, we are truly grateful to the respondents of our research. Your willingness to share your personal experiences has been invaluable to our study. Your openness and honesty have enriched our understanding of the challenges faced by nurses transitioning without an induction program. We appreciate the contributions of each individual who has played a role in this research, and we are excited to share our findings with the broader community. Thank you for being an essential part of this journey.

REFERENCES

- Adams, W. C. (2015). Conducting Semi-Structured Interviews. 492–505.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>
- Alhazmi, A. A., & Kaufmann, A. (2022). Phenomenological Qualitative Methods Applied to the Analysis of Cross-Cultural Experience in Novel Educational Social Contexts. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.785134>
- Alnuqaidan, H., Alhajraf, A., Mathew, P., & Ahmad, M. (2021). Transitional Shock of Multi-Nationality Newly Graduate Nurses in Kuwait. *SAGE Open Nursing*, 7, 237796082199853. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2377960821998530>
- Cai, T. (2021). Transition of newly graduated nurses in China: An evaluation study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 50, 102951.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102951>
- Cao, X., Li, J., & Gong, S. (2021). The relationships of both transition shock, empathy, resilience and coping strategies with professional quality of life in newly graduated nurses. *BMC Nursing*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00589-0>
- Chen, F., Liu, Y., Wang, X., & Dong, H. (2021). Transition shock, preceptor support and nursing competency among newly graduated registered nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Nurse Education Today*, 102, 104891.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104891>

- Clipper, B., & Cherry, B. (2015). From Transition Shock to Competent Practice: Developing Preceptors to Support New Nurse Transition. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 46(10), 448–454. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20150918-02>
- Dames, S. (2019). The interplay of developmental factors that impact congruence and the ability to thrive among new graduate nurses: A qualitative study of the interplay as students transition to professional practice. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 36, 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.02.013>
- Duchscher, J. B., & Windey, M. (2018). Stages of Transition and Transition Shock. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 34(4), 228–232. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nnd.0000000000000461>
- Duchscher, J. E. B. (2009). Transition shock: the initial stage of role adaptation for newly graduated Registered Nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 65(5), 1103–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2008.04898.x>
- Dukes, S. (1984). Phenomenological methodology in the human sciences. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 23(3), 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00990785>
- Heidegger, M. (1962). Being and time. In J. Macquarrie, & E. Robinson, (Trans.), *New York, NY: Harper & Row*.
- Husserl, E. (1913/1982). Ideas pertaining to a pure phenomenology and to a phenomenological philosophy—first book: general introduction to pure phenomenology. Trans. F. Kersten. The Hague, Netherlands: Nijhoff.
- Irwin, C., Bliss, J., & Poole, K. (2018). Does Preceptorship improve confidence and competence in Newly Qualified Nurses: A systematic literature review. *Nurse Education Today*, 60, 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2017.09.011>
- Kaihlanen, A. M., Strandell-Laine, C., & Salminen, L. (2016). Towards unpredictable - The anticipations of nursing students of the transition to a registered nurse. *Nursing and Palliative Care*, 1(4), 94–96. <https://doi.org/10.15761/npc.1000124>
- Kramer, M. (1974). *Reality Shock: Why Nurses Leave Nursing*. St Louis: C.V Mosby Company.
- Kukkonen, P., Leino-Kilpi, H., Koskinen, S., Salminen, L., & Strandell-Laine, C. (2019). Nurse managers' perceptions of the competence of newly graduated nurses: A scoping review. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 28(1), 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12891>
- Labrague, L. J. (2023). Relationship between transition shock in novice emergency room nurses, quality of nursing care, and adverse patient events: The mediating role of emotional exhaustion. *Australasian Emergency Care*, 27(1), 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.auec.2023.07.001>
- Labrague, L., & McEnroe-Petitte, D. (2018). Job stress in new nurses during the transition period: an integrative review. *International Nursing Review*, 65(4), 491–504. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inr.12425>
- Laschinger, H. K. S., Cummings, G., Leiter, M., Wong, C., MacPhee, M., Ritchie, J., Wolff, A., Regan, S., Rhéaume-Brüning, A., Jeffs, L., Young-Ritchie, C., Grinspun, D., Gurnham, M. E., Foster, B., Huckstep, S., Ruffolo, M., Shamian, J., Burkoski, V., Wood, K., & Read, E. (2016). Starting Out: A time-lagged study of new graduate nurses' transition to practice. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 57, 82–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2016.01.005>

- Lee, Y., & Oh, Y. (2020). Levels, antecedents, and consequences of critical thinking among clinical nurses: a quantitative literature review. *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions*, 17, 26. <https://doi.org/10.3352/jeehp.2020.17.26>
- Lewis, S., & McGowan, B. (2015). Newly qualified nurses' experiences of a preceptorship. *British Journal of Nursing*, 24(1), 40–43. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2015.24.1.40>
- Mazzella-Ebstein, A. M., Tan, K. S., Panageas, K. S., Arnetz, J. E., & Barton-Burke, M. (2021). The Emotional Intelligence, Occupational Stress, and Coping Characteristics by Years of Nursing Experiences of Newly Hired Oncology Nurses. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 8(4), 352–359. <https://doi.org/10.4103/apjon.apjon-2117>
- Merleau-Ponty, M. (1962). *Phenomenology of perception* (C. Smith, Trans.). London: Routledge & Kegan Paul (original work published 1945).
- Ortiz, J. (2016). New graduate nurses' experiences about lack of professional confidence. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 19, 19–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2016.04.001>
- Patton. M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Quek, G. J., & Shorey, S. (2018). Perceptions, Experiences, and Needs of Nursing Preceptors and Their Preceptees on Preceptorship: An Integrative Review. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 34(5), 417–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.profnurs.2018.05.003>
- Rogers, S., Lai, J., Walker, A., Rawson, H., & Redley, B. (2023). Development of work readiness in graduate nurses during a Transition to Practice Program: A survey study. *Collegian Journal of the Royal College of Nursing Australia*, 30(4), 595–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2023.05.007>
- Roze des Ordon, A., Cheng, A., Gaudet, J., Downar, J., & Lockyer, J. (2018). Adapting Feedback to Individual Residents: An Examination of Preceptor Challenges and Approaches. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 10(2), 168–175. <https://doi.org/10.4300/jgme-d-17-00590.1>
- Rush, K. L., Janke, R., Duchscher, J. E., Phillips, R., & Kaur, S. (2019). Best practices of formal new graduate transition programs: An integrative review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 94, 139–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2019.02.010>
- Smith, J. A., Flowers, P., & Larkin, M. (2009). *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research*. London: Sage.
- Su, Q., Jiang, M., Yun, B., Ma, Y., Zuo, Y., & Han, L. (2020). Effect of clinical teaching behaviours on transition shock in graduate nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 77(2), 763–774. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.14635>
- Su, Q., Wu, Y., Yun, B., Zhang, H., She, D., & Han, L. (2023). The mediating effect of clinical teaching behavior on transition shock and career identity among new nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Nurse Education Today*, 125, 105780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2023.105780>
- Tarhan, M., Kaya, D. A., Tetik, N., & Karayılan, S. (2023). Relationship Between Style of Coping with Stress and Level of Transition Shock Among New Graduate Nurses:

- A Cross-Sectional Study. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 54(8), 350–359. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20230711-05>
- Van Manen, M. (1997) *Researching Lived Experience: Human Science for an Action Sensitive Pedagogy*. 2nd Edition, Althouse Press, London.
- Wakefield, E. (2018). Is your graduate nurse suffering from transition shock? *Journal of Perioperative Nursing*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.26550/2209-1092.1024>
- Wierzbinski-Cross, H., Ward, K., & Baumann, P. (2015). Nurses' Perceptions of Nurse Residency. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 31(1), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nnd.0000000000000100>
- Woo, M. W. J., & Newman, S. A. (2019). The experience of transition from nursing students to newly graduated registered nurses in Singapore. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 7(1), 81–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2019.11.002>
- Zhang, Y., Yu, X., Lu, X., Tang, Y., Jiang, W., Wei, Q., & Wei, L. (2023). Safety Behavior and Transition Shock among Newly Graduated Nurses: The Mediating Role of Feedback-Seeking Behavior. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 2023, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9699240>